

Peer mentoring, school development and professional development

The role of mentorship and its importance as a part of professional development
within the mother-tongue teaching profession

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Introduction

This paper focuses on action research in practice and the mentoring process within the teaching profession.

As an employee in the education system in Norway, I would like to investigate in depth my engagement in the profession as a mentor: How can I, as a mentor, contribute to improving the working conditions for a group of mother-tongue teachers?-in particular.

The study aims to define problems within the mother-tongue teaching profession, identify challenges, and explore problem-solving approaches.

- **The concept of mentoring**

Mentoring is a way of learning in almost all spheres of life and work. Mentoring serves as an agent of improving the quality of the individual's work and the organisation's work as a whole. The world is developing a mentoring culture to train and improve the quality of work in various fields, particularly in education.

Mentoring is a complex, interactive process between individuals at different levels of experience and expertise, in which the expert (mentor) provides support to their colleague to become more efficient in their work and to contribute to achieving the institution's goals where they work. The ultimate goal is professional development and career advancement.

Also, when we discuss modern teaching characteristics regarding methodology and strategy in the mentoring process, we emphasise that the student is at the centre of the teaching process. Teaching and learning are the transmission and adoption of content, as well as a form of training that students can apply through the influential models in the work. In seeking answers through questions and action research, peer guidance appears to be an effective tool for achieving better, more effective teaching goals. An experienced co-worker is a nexus between teacher, student and other colleagues. 'Applied to teach' work to improve student achievement and school development considers analysing the effects of teaching and collaborative strategies, and student/teacher psychology in certain situations and contexts.

To discover effective mentorship strategies, teachers need to rely on knowledge of their own students, their subject, and their position in the school environment. Mentoring involves enhancing the independent work of co-workers and students under the guidance and supervision of a mentor, and it can be successfully applied in every school or educational institution.

Mentoring is a relationship in which both parties can benefit, whether it is a young teacher or an experienced colleague who needs a counsellor and guide through school life and professional development, or a mentor who wants to invest their time and expertise in guiding another person's development. Through mentoring, the mentor perfects active listening techniques and asks the right questions that indicate new directions of thinking and acting. At the same time, a mentor will gain insight into how other colleagues think, especially if they have gone through a different education system and training. Also, the professional network and contacts are usually extended throughout the process, enabling future cooperation. At the same time, mentee¹ will receive targeted, professional support from a colleague in the same field who understands the specifics of teaching, one of the rare jobs in which full responsibility is expected from the very beginning.

A mentor is, first and foremost, a friend. Lauvås, Lycke and Handal, in their book *Kollegaveiledning med kritiske venner*, explain the notion of ‘critic friendship’ (Lauvås 2016: 15):

A critical friend provides feedback to an individual—a student, a teacher, or an administrator—or to a group. A critical friend, as the name suggests, is a trusted person who asks provocative questions, provides data to be examined through another lens, and offers critique of a person’s work as a friend. A critical friend takes the time to fully understand the context of the work presented and the outcomes that the person or group is working toward. The friend is an advocate for the success of that work. (Costa 1993: 49-50)

¹ A person who is advised, trained, or counselled by a mentor.

According to Lauvås, a ‘critical friendship’ consists of five stages:

- A personal relationship of trust
- A trust that your critical friend has professional expertise
- Respect for the personal integrity of the mentor
- Essential assurance that the critical friend wishes you well
- Mentor’s empathy

For that reason, mentors’ roles may differ. The mentor could be a counsellor, a contributor or a leader. By taking different roles in the work, the mentor provides precisely the type of support that the teacher/fellow worker needs most at that time. As a counsellor, the mentor’s responsibilities and tasks are the most extensive. As the process progresses, the roles change (from contributor to leader). The supervised person takes on most responsibilities and tasks, while the mentor only guides them through the process.

Methodology

Action research as a method for better practice within the teaching profession

Action research within the practice is a tool for professional development. It is a constructive interaction between practice and theory. Through an exploratory attitude towards practice and theory, the teacher questions their way of being a teacher with a view to understanding and improving existing practice (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 1999).²

According to Ulvik, Riese and Roness, the experience with action research methodology in practice in teacher education has shown that it is challenging to both learn and study, and to teach and perform action research simultaneously (Ulvik 2021: 161).

However, this methodology raises profound questions that lead to awareness of the situation we face every day as teachers and educators. The model of the research, according to McNiff,³ has been shown as practical if the teacher-researcher implements the following questions in research:

- How can I improve my own instructions?
 - What am I interested in researching?
 - Why do I want to investigate this?
 - How can I learn more about the topic?
 - What can I do?
 - How can I evaluate the measure?
 - How can I explain the result?
 - How will I change my practice in light of the evaluation?
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² In Ulvik, Marit; Riese Hanne; Roness, Dag. 2021. *Å forske på egen praksis*. Bergen. Fagbokforlaget (s.161)

³ McNiff, 2002, about action research as a method

Researching within your own practice has advantages, but also some disadvantages, for example: empower the professional, those who are familiar with the problem and questions develop itself within new and practice-based knowledge (Cochran-Smith et al., 2009), can become “a house blind” which explains the phenomenon when one is not able to see and perceive the situation realistically around himself (Gudmundsdottir, 1998).

- Observation as a method

Observation is one of the key elements during the process. The observation can be conducted during the class or teaching performance, or as a tool within another method, such as a focus group. One of the most commonly used techniques in class evaluation is observation, which can be appropriate (random, unsystematic) or planned (objective observation). Appropriate observation is not prepared; it is superficial and unreliable, so it cannot be the basis for an objective assessment of the class’s or the interview's didactic efficiency.

Planned observations are based on predefined goals. Precise determination of the goal of the class, interview, or session observation provides clear guidelines for preparing instruments to record specific activities in class, interview, or session.

This reduces the likelihood that some crucial elements will escape objective assessment. Different methods, scales, checklists, evidence lists, and so on can be used in planned observation.

Observation is a complex process. This is the time spent in the classroom and includes the time devoted to preparing for the observation and to the conversation after completing the class's observation.

According to Dalland (2017), our observations are not accurate but rather relative, person-dependent interpretations of reality, all based on our own standpoint. Our observations are in context.

- Focus group interview as a method

A Focus group interview is a research method in which the researcher gathers group participants for a conversation about an issue. The participants in the focus group should have some standard

references. The researcher "throws out" a question or assertion and tries to spark a conversation among the group participants. The researcher can be more or less active in the conversation – this depends on the group dynamics and how easily the participants themselves start the conversation. The researcher "controls" the conversation to talk about it, which is relevant to the problem. Focus group discussions are often semi-structured interview guides with one or more statements, keywords, or questions as the basis for conversation/discussion in a group.

The researchers find some advantages and disadvantages of this method. According to Ekornes (2021), we see what we focus on. The focus group interview is more than just individual interview data, as it creates meaning in group conversations. Participants must argue and explain the issue. This makes their opinions clearer. Also, we can ask directly why they have different opinions, rather than just ponder it by comparing individual interview data.

Ekornes pointed out that sometimes it could be difficult for participants to focus on the exact issue. Interviews can «disrupt» the members, and the research can have a polarising effect. Also, it could be challenging to be effective as a mentor within the process.

- Analysis of focus group data

Analysis should be based on understanding, which depends on a scientific and theoretical perspective. The researcher should focus more on the dialogues performed than on isolated statements. Responses are also a crucial part of this process. As one phase of research and investigation, analysis leads us to discover cause-and-effect relationships. This method allows us to explore the details related to the event by drawing conclusions and analysing experiences.

Action research within the teaching profession: findings and evaluation

In this article, the action research within the education system in Bergen, Norway, will be further elaborated.

The action was driven through a group of mother-tongue teachers employed in *Bergen kommune*. The research examined teachers' attitudes toward mentoring, their position within the teaching milieu, and their participation in professional development. The obtained results show that teachers considered mentoring extremely important in the context of lifelong learning and confirmed that it is applicable at all levels.

However, they point out that they lack knowledge of peer mentoring and support to implement this role in their work environment or within a group. Through observation of everyday work, mother-tongue teachers point out many objective obstacles to applying the mentoring role and its strategy as an effective professional development tool within their working group.

The first action: the action research was conducted in one of the base schools for mother-tongue teaching within Bergen municipality, *Bergen kommune*. The group of six mother-tongue teachers participated voluntarily. The focus time or focus group interview was used as a method for 90 minutes. The goal was to define the profession's problems and challenges in the everyday working environment.

Data collection:

Data is obtained from six mother-tongue teachers employed in *Bergen kommune* (Bergen commune). The group worked interactively, divided into two groups (3+3) during the planning and professional development day in February 2021. The participants were asked to focus on the issues they experience every day during their working time. The goal was to define problems within the profession, identify challenges, and explore problem-solving. The guidance was given to them in the form of questions to try to answer, and to concentrate, preventively, on themselves as individuals and as professional mother-tongue teachers.

Round 1: On the planning day, 5th February 2021, the group was given permission to implement the action research within the mother-tongue teaching profession. They had an hour and a half to choose the topic that describes an issue or potential issue within the profession, interactively discuss the topic with other peers in the group based on given questions, and use reflection as a final action method for transformative learning.

The questions I prepared as a mentor, which were used to start the discussion, are as follows, according to Lauvås' model (Lauvås 2016: 60):

Can you please tell me what has happened?

What kind of feelings have you experienced?

How have you reacted?

What have you noticed? (about yourself and the others)

What good thing have you done so far? What were you satisfied with? How do you know that?

What did not go so well? What were you not satisfied with? How do you know that?

This round was finished with a summary of my understanding of the cases and minor corrections of those under the mentoring process.

Findings and evaluation:

During the session, this information is obtained:

1. The last scheduled class in the timetable is an issue for mother-tongue teachers. Pupils often cannot concentrate on learning and feel excluded from the regular group, especially when playtime is scheduled as the last class.
2. Parent-teacher conferences and meetings - mother-tongue teachers are excluded from the practice. The purpose of an inclusive approach was discussed as essential for children with special needs. A mother-tongue teacher has a better overview and more personal contact with the pupil during the individual teaching time. Therefore, the presence of the mother-tongue teacher at parent-teacher conferences and meetings is crucial.

3. Communication culture is not established within the *Bergen kommune* (Bergen municipality) school system. The communication is poorly driven in this direction: homeroom teachers with mother-tongue teachers, directors of the base-schools between themselves ⁴, the school which provides the actual teaching for the pupils in communication between mother-tongue teacher and the leadership team of the actual school, the Agency for schools within the municipality (Etat for skole) with teaching staff and directors of the schools.

4. Junior High School-Adapted education is without a goal. Poor leadership and guidance were not provided on an individual basis, despite students' right to be followed up by a mother-tongue teacher.

5. Budget – There is no budget for mother-tongue teachers for materials. The requests are usually declined.

6. Pupils with special needs, including mother-tongue classes- Mother-tongue teachers do not have any support or professional training. Regarding the issue, the conclusion is that the system treats them as assistants rather than as teachers.

7. Pandemic and digital lecturing- This is a challenge for every teaching staff member. Mother-tongue teachers are not spared either. The reference is given in the form of criticism of the work of the heads of the school departments. The testimony explains that they do not answer calls or emails and do not include mother-tongue teachers discussing the strategy or digital ethics.

8. Differences in primary culture, ethics, and religion could be an issue in establishing a good and healthy relationship between mother-tongue teachers and their pupils. The three teachers' testimony in the group of six indicated low self-esteem and workflow issues related to the aforementioned challenges within the profession.⁵

⁴ The base-schools within Bergen kommune: Rothaugen skole, Hop oppvekststun skole, Lynghaug skole, Åstveit Skole, Møhlenpris skole, Skjold skole, Seljedalen skole, Nygårdslie skole, Olsvik skole, Slettebakken skole, Ny Krohnborg - avdeling skole, Ytre Arna skole.

⁵ Different ethnic and religious groups. Some pupils decline to have the individual class with a teacher of another religion or from a country at war.

9. Professional development- There is a need for more development time within the profession. A timeslot for development and planning, including workshops, should be part of a regular practice for every teaching staff member. Mother-tongue teachers have the same rights as the regular teaching staff. The team's collaborative planning is more than urgent.

Six of the nine pieces of information collected have come from any subject teacher employed in Bergen municipality, as a testimony of PED fellow peers at the University of Bergen employed as teachers in *Bergen kommune*. What is described here are issues that concern the entire teaching staff, not just the mother tongue teacher.

The three most distinctive points in the action regarding mother-tongue teachers, in particular, are those mentioned above: 3, 8, and 9. This is the specific characterisation of an issue within the mother tongue teaching profession.

The second action:

The second action is based on the questionnaire for mother-tongue teachers employed in Bergen kommune. This questionnaire shows quantitative results.

Round 2: The questionnaire contains 21 questions, 44 subquestions and seeks information about:

- Background information
- Initial education and professional development
- Collaboration with other teachers employed in *Bergen kommune* and parents of students
- Working ethics in the base school and schools' mother-tongue teacher visits

Data collection:

In the quantitative examination, seven respondents participated voluntarily and gave answers anonymously:

1. 42,9 % men; 57,1 women
2. 57,1 % of respondents came to Norway from Europe, 14,3% from Africa, 14,3% from North America and 14,3% from Asia

3. All of the respondents are full-time employees
4. 42,9% of respondents are educated at the bachelor level, 28,6% have a master's degree, 14,3% of respondents have an old form of the bachelor's degree with 240 ECTS, 14,3% have a PhD
5. Professional qualifications during the teacher education-**Knowledge and skills related to reading competence**: on the scale of 1-5, 28,6% ticked no.3, 28,6 ticked no.4, and 42,9% ticked no.5
6. Professional qualifications during the studying period of teacher education- **Pedagogy of reading competence: knowledge and methodology for reading competence, instructional skills (teaching of reading comprehension strategies, the structure of texts or literature)**: on the scale of 1-5, 28,6% ticked no.3, 28,6 ticked no.4, and 42,9% ticked no.5
7. Professional qualifications during the st teacher education- **General pedagogical knowledge: e.g. teacher-student interaction, classroom management, school evaluation, special education**: on the scale of 1-5, 14,3% ticked no.2, 57,1 ticked no.4 and 28,6% ticked no.5
8. Studying the following areas as part of formal teacher education and/or training:

Language and literature: 1, just an overview or introduction to the topic; 6 it was the focus area

Pedagogy/teaching (language): 1 not at all; 6 it was the focus area

Educational psychology: 1 not at all; 4 just an overview or introduction to the topic; 2 it was the focus area

Theoretical models and processes for reading: 1 not at all; 4 just an overview or introduction to the topic; 2 it was the focus area

Special education: 3 not at all; 3 just an overview or introduction to the topic; 1 it was the focus area

Pedagogy/teaching as a second or foreign language: 1 just an overview or introduction to the topic; 6 it was the focus area

Assessment methods in reading comprehension: 4 just an overview or introduction to the topic; 3 it was the focus area

9. Obligatory requirements within professional development activities:

85,7% answered yes, and 14,3% answered no.

10. Professional development activities devoted during the last twelve months:

Reading skills: knowledge and skills related to reading competence

On the scale of 1-6, 14,3% ticked no.1; 14,3% ticked no.3; 14,3% ticked no.4; 28,6% ticked no.5, and 28,6% ticked no.6

Pedagogy of reading skills: knowledge and methodology of reading skills, instruction skills (teaching of reading comprehension strategies, text structure or literature)

On the scale of 1-6, 14,3% ticked no.1; 14,3% ticked no.3; 28,6% ticked no.4; 28,6% ticked no.5, and 14,3% ticked no.6

General pedagogical knowledge: i.e. teacher-student interaction, classroom leading, school evaluation, special education

On the scale of 1-6, 14,3% ticked no.2; 42,9% ticked no.3; 14,3% ticked no.4; 14,3% ticked no.5, and 14,3% ticked no.6

11. The listed courses included in the teacher education or other professional qualifications within the professional activities (multiple choices)

Knowledge and understanding of my subject field: 6 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 3 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Pedagogical skills in the teaching of my subject field: 6 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 2 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Knowledge of the curriculum: 4 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 5 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Student assessment practice: 5 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 3 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

ICT (information and communication technology) skills for teaching: 4 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 5 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Student behaviour and classroom leading: 7 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 0 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

School management and administration: 1 answer- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 1 answer- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Approaches to individualised learning: 1 answer- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 3 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Teaching students with special needs: 1 answer- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 3 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Teaching in a multicultural or multilingual setting: 4 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 4 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

The teaching of interdisciplinary skills (i.e. problem-solving, learning to learn): 4 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 3 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Student career guidance and counselling: 3 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 1 answer- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Internal evaluation or self-evaluation of schools: 1 answer- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 2 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Use of evaluation results: 1 answer- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 2 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Teacher-parent collaboration: 5 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 2 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Second language teaching: 5 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 2 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Communication with people from different cultures or countries: 4 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 3 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

Teaching about equity and diversity: 3 answers- Included in my teacher education or other professional qualification; 2 answers- Included in my professional development activities over the last 12 months

12. Use of digital devices (such as a tablet, computer, smartphone, e-reader or interactive whiteboard) has been used in mother tongue teaching in the last month

100% of respondents answered yes

13. Requirements for students to use digital devices over the last month for any of the following purposes:

Search for subject-related information online: 7 respondents answered yes

Work on extended projects (i.e. over several weeks): 4 respondents answered yes, and three respondents answered no

Work on short assignments (i.e. within a week): 7 respondents answered yes

Work at your individual pace: 7 respondents answered yes

Work with individualised material: 7 respondents answered yes

Plan a sequence of learning activities for yourself: 2 respondents answered yes, and five respondents answered no

Submission of homework: 4 respondents answered yes, and three respondents answered no

Practice: 6 respondents answered yes, and one respondent answered no

Coordination of school work with other students: 2 respondents answered yes, and five respondents answered no

Follow-up of missed lessons or material: 6 respondents answered yes, and one respondent answered no

Reading texts electronically instead of paper versions: 6 respondents answered yes, and one respondent answered no

Write a text like a blog or a wiki: 1 respondent answered yes, and six respondents answered no

14. Statements about regular collaboration between co-teachers in mother tongue lessons

We discuss the performance requirements for mother-tongue teaching: 2 answered as disagree; 3 answered as agree; 2 answered as totally agree

We discuss the criteria we use to prepare our lessons: 5 answered as disagreeing; 2 answered as totally agree

We exchange assignments for lessons and homework that cover many different levels of difficulty: 1 answered as completely disagree; 1 answered as disagreeing; 4 answered as agree; 1 answered as totally agree

I prepared a selection of teaching units together with my co-teachers in mother tongue teaching: 2 answered as completely disagree; 3 answered as disagree; 2 answered as totally agree

We discuss ways to teach our students learning strategies and techniques: 5 answered as agree; 2 answered as totally agree

My mother tongue colleagues benefit from my specific skills and interests: 1 answered as completely disagree; 1 answered as disagree; 4 answered as agree; 1 answered as totally agree

We discuss ways to identify students' individual strengths and weaknesses better: 1 answered as completely disagree; 1 answered as disagree; 3 answered as agree; 2 answered as totally agree

15. Familiarity with the new curriculum for mother-tongue teaching (UDIR, 2020)

100% answered yes

16. The availability of the curriculum content for mother-tongue subject (e.g. parent-teacher conferences/meetings, student development meeting or a newsletter) to parents: 71,4% answered no, and 28,6 % answered yes

17. Familiarity with the rules that apply to the use of digital devices for teaching: 85,7 answered yes, and 14,3 answered no

18. Safety at work: 85,7% answered yes as they feel safe at work, and 14,3% answered no as they do not feel safe at work

19. Experienced discomfort related to religious or cultural differences at the current workplace: 42,9% answered yes, as they experienced discomfort to some extent, and 57,1% answered no, as they did not experience any discomfort at the current workplace

Findings and evaluation:

The findings show that most mother-tongue teacher employees hold stable positions within *Bergen kommune*. The answers show that most of them are treated fairly and correctly by their

employer and colleagues. More or less, some issues can arise regarding religious and cultural misunderstandings in the teacher-student-parent relationship.

Many mother-tongue teachers employed within *Bergen kommune* are highly educated professionals. Some mother-tongue teachers lack formal education or training in language and literature, which is necessary for this profession. According to UDIR, the competency requirements are rather general than focusing on language as a subject:

- Teacher education from the home country;
- Three-year education for bilingual teachers;
- Higher education of at least three years, including pedagogical education, where one and a half years include the language and culture.

It appeared that some engineers, economists, and people from other professions with pedagogical education (60 ECTS) are, or could be, employed as mother-tongue teachers if their native language is the one the employer requires. In practice, these people struggle to create tasks for students, teach the language, or evaluate students' reading and writing comprehension and literacy.

According to the quantitative findings, the recommendation to leadership is to focus on providing relevant workshops and training on developing competencies and skills in the aforementioned topics and issues. The other option would be to provide the relevant education through continuing education and a temporary arrangement programme offered by UDIR. In practice, mother-tongue teachers are rarely offered the possibility to continue their education, as they are not recognised as a valuable resource within the education system.

In general, *Bergen kommune* is recognised as a good employer by employees. As in any other profession, employers should consider certain factors when investing in good professional development. Segments that should be improved in practice include communication regarding the *Etaten*-director of the school-employee, better positioning and acknowledgement of the efforts of mother-tongue teachers, and prioritising professional development equally for all employees in *Bergen kommune* in terms of continuing education, relevant workshops, courses, and so on. Also, within professional development activities, base-schools leadership should be

focusing on more interactive class preparation among fellow peers, preferably mixed groups with class and mother-tongue teachers, as transparency of the class goals is missing.

The third action:

Presentation of the findings and results to the leadership. The leadership's perspective is elaborated below:

The leadership team was initially interested in hearing more about the findings and the topics examined. By the time, there was a slight change in the initial interest. The leadership claimed that they are still interested in hearing about issues within the profession and potential solutions regarding professional development and improvement of the profession, but that would be time-consuming at this point and cannot be prioritised over the other obligations, i.e., preparing for the next school year, the potential strike of the teaching staff and so on.

Findings and evaluation:

With all due respect and an understanding of the importance and responsibility of the work entrusted to the leadership, if there is no time to address the problems and the status of mother-tongue teachers in the sector, prosperity in the professional field cannot be expected.

Conclusion

- Learning through the process

Educated mentors go through the process of everyday learning. This is the role in which the leader has full responsibility for the mentee's work results. In a learning-oriented mentoring process, the mentor influences the mentee's professional development, both emotionally and intellectually. This clearly structured entry of the mentee into the profession traces their learning path and advancement. The mentoring process begins with establishing a learning-oriented relationship and continues with its maintenance. The mentor's role in this relationship is to maintain balance.

The knowledge and skills acquired through this process are:

- how adults learn;
- the role of mentoring in professional development;
- developmental stages of mentees;
- relations between mentors and mentees;
- roles of mentors (advisor, associate, leader);
- techniques of observation;
- monitoring and evaluation (criteria and techniques);
- knowledge of the program and initial studies;
- research methodology;
- recognition of needs and choice activities for own professional development;

- verbal and nonverbal communication (active listening, asking questions);
- establishment and maintenance of the relationship mentor-mentee (relationship based on trust, respect for individuality),
- observation and recording;
- teamwork;
- assessment;
- giving constructive feedback;
- self-assessment and action planning.

One of the crucial skills gained through the process is good communication and active listening. Active listening signals support and establish a safe environment for shared reflection. In addition, personal capacities to understand and provide better support to the mentee are increasing.

For the mentor to actively listen, his or her attention must be focused on what the mentee wants to communicate. However, it often happens that, during the listening process, the interlocutor is directed towards himself rather than towards the one he is listening to. This shift towards oneself interferes with understanding. It is significant for mentors who are focused on learning to be aware of this.

- The way forward

Emotional security is necessary for providing cognitive complexity. Supporting a mentee emotionally, intellectually, and physically advances the mentee's development toward the next steps in the profession (e.g., from a mentee to a teacher with experience, a competent teacher, etc.). By carefully balancing support and challenge, mentors should provide a safe environment in which nonverbal and verbal communication signals full attention and high expectations from

the mentee. These components allow the mentor and the mentee to exchange questions, concerns, information, and shortcomings related to different skills.

Efforts should be made, whenever possible, to involve the envisaged activities of mentors with other co-workers/mentees. It could be an integral part of implementing other initiatives in the school, so that mentors would not have additional workload. For example, different activities in working with a beginner teacher or a new colleague can fit into professional development activities at the school/kindergarten level (information on teaching methods and their application, inclusive education and individualisation of the teaching process, open classes, discussions and round tables, etc.). Thus, many activities from the mentor work program with a mentee can be placed in the context of specific relevant initiatives that already exist.

However, the work of a mentor benefits the institution: a better working atmosphere in the collective, a lifelong learning atmosphere among all employees, satisfied staff members, growing self-confidence among teachers, good work that reflects on the institution's goals and productivity, and so on.

Successful cooperation between mentors and leadership creates a working environment that helps the institution achieve its goals more efficiently and effectively.

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